
ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3893529>
УДК 351.746.

Nguyen Linh Khieu

Nguyen Linh Khieu, Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Assistant Professor, Vietnam National University, Hanoi, Vietnam. E-mail: nguyenlinhkhieu@mail.ru.

Coping with negative impacts of non-traditional security in ethnic minority areas in Russian Federation and experience for Vietnam

Abstract. The Russian Federation is a multi-ethnic nation. Like other countries in the world, the Russian Federation is also facing enormous security challenges in which the non-traditional security challenge in ethnic minority regions is an issue that attracts research attention from various aspects. The resolutions of the Russian Federation for these challenges can be a valuable experience for other countries, including Vietnam. In this article, the author identifies the fundamentals of the non-traditional security challenges of the Russian Federation, analyzes the achievements of coping with the negative impacts of non-traditional security factors of the Russian Federation and draws out important lessons.

Key words: Non-traditional security, ethnic minorities, Russian Federation, policy.

The article is the result of implementing the topic «Non-traditional security of ethnic minorities in Vietnam today: current status and solutions». Ethnic Work Code 12.17/16-20.

The Russian Federation is a multi-ethnic nation with more than 185 ethnic groups. Ethnic groups of Russia are very diverse. Russian ethnic group accounts for 81.53%, Tatar 3.76%, Ukrainian 2.97%, Chuvash 1.21%, Bashkir 0.92%, Belarus 0.82%, Moldova 0.73%, Chechnia 0.61 %, Germany 0.57% and other ethnic groups. Of the 85 entities that make up the Russian Federation, there are 21 ethnic minority regions, 5 okrugs autonomous regions and 1 autonomous region (mainly ethnic minorities) [3].

Non-traditional security challenges for the Russian Federation

Non-traditional security appeared after the «cold war». It is different from traditional security. If traditional security is a threat to the survival of the nation and people from wars of aggression and military intervention, non-traditional security consists of factors that directly affect the human life, the survival of the community and the people. Non-traditional security includes elements, such as: Terrorism, climate change, environmental disaster, epidemics, smuggling, transnational crime, energy crisis, food crisis, ethnic & religious conflicts, etc. In the current context of transformation, the Russian Federation is facing a lot of challenges related to non-traditional security.

Firstly, challenges from the West with the intention of approaching the Western border and the European region the Russian Federation, compete and push the Russian Federation away from Europe. External hostile forces have pursued a provocative path based on national and religious issues towards the Russian Federation. To address this challenge, the Russian Federation needs to proactively consolidate its economic potential and ensure socio-political stability in its territory.

Secondly, the challenge from the Eastern Islamic world. The Eastern Islamic world not only bases on racial and cultural intimacy, the desire to draw not only Central Asian republic countries and Kavkaz countries into its sphere of influence, but also approaches and entices autonomous Islamic territories within the composition of the Russian Federation. To prevent it, the Russian Federation needs to rely on the progressive elements of the Islamic culture and the mankind's culture in general to combat Islamic extremist elements. In addition, it is necessary to ensure that the power structures in the autonomous regions are not Islamized or radicalized, and pay attention to propagating and educating the common community spirit of people from the Eurasian background.

Thirdly, challenges from the dynamic development and strong rise of several countries in the Asia-Pacific Region with global ambitions are plotting to turn the Far East and Russia Federation's Syria became a new type of colony, a region that provides direct and unforeseen materials for these ambitions. This is not a new problem for many other regions of the world, but this threat to the Russian Federation is difficult because the Far East and Syria themselves are very remote peripheries, with undeveloped economy and society, difficult transportation, harsh natural conditions, and extremely sparse population, mainly ethnic minorities.

Non-traditional security challenges of ethnic minorities in the Russian Federation

Non-traditional security of ethnic minority regions is transnational, trans-regional and trans-territorial issues that directly affect

the lives of ethnic minorities and threaten the stability and sustainable development of certain ethnic minority communities. The non-traditional security challenges of ethnic minorities often arise around human security, economic security, political security, socio-cultural security, environmental security and ethnic security. In the current context, ethnic minorities in the Russian Federation seem to have some non-traditional security challenges, namely:

(1) Population decline, birth/death rate of ethnic groups in correlation with one another in a country or territory leads to changes in the proportion of population of each ethnic group in the common structure, which can be the cause for challenges and threats. In the Russian Federation, while the Russian ethnic group has a low birth rate, a relatively high mortality rate, and the population tends to decrease in absolute succession for decades, some other ethnic groups have experienced a population boom. However, the population boom of these ethnic groups actually only contributes to rebalancing the proportion of the population between the Russian ethnic group and other ethnic minorities living together, but cannot contribute to limiting the plunging population trend in the Russian Federation at present. In 2018, the United Nations forecast that the Russian Federation's population will decline to 132 million by 2050.

(2) Migration issue. The mechanical migration processes also bring risks and challenges. Moreover, these threats and challenges are formed in a relatively short period, so the social psychology on the basis of ethnic and race factors is very difficult to adapt. Furthermore, there are risks of overloaded labor market, social services as well as the emergence of new and «non-traditional» races in the territory with hidden risk of conflicts, the boycott of the old ethnic groups and the isolation of new ethnic communities.

The migration flows crossing the borders of countries always complicate the ethnic structure of many countries and territories. Also from this process, a «cultural shock» appears among immigrants or chau-

vinism from local ethnic groups. This also appears popularly in ethnic minority regions in the Russian Federation.

Migration is also an important factor affecting the population of ethnic minorities in the Russian Federation. The statistics for the 2008-2010 period show that the number of migrants coming to the Russian Federation was from Armenia was about 50-100 thousand people; and from Azerbaijanis was 20-50 thousand people; and from Georgia was less than 5 thousand people [2].

(3) Human security. Russian researchers believe that the challenges of human security depend on the response of the state. Human security is threatened because the state does not guarantee necessary conditions and cannot prevent threats. For example, the state cannot prevent and control the widespread of crime, violence, and free operation; weak and ineffective government in management and administration; social morality deterioration in a significant proportion of social members; corruption of the contingent of officials; expansion of power and benefits of criminal groups – mafia; system of mass media imposed the individualism ideology and foreign values on the society; the illicit enrichment of a small social group on the back of poverty, impoverishment of the majority in the society, especially ethnic minorities and immigrants.

(4) Economic security. The strong development process and economic integration also pose different risks in the non-traditional security areas of ethnic minority regions. The innovation, industrialization and modernization have impacted on a number of long-standing and traditional production industries, new industries, etc. These processes have made a part of ethnic minority people separate from long-term jobs for living, traditional lifestyle, but unable to adapt to new jobs and lifestyle. Under these conditions, there may be a «cultural labor division», representing different ethnic groups and races engaging in different jobs or different producing sectors. Such type of labor division deepens the boundaries and gaps among ethnic groups, increases the iso-

lation and closeness as well as forms prejudices based on racial issues.

(5) Non-traditional security in the fields of national culture, ethnic culture, belief and religion. Non-traditional cultural security factors are particularly relevant to preserving the voice of ethnic groups and the process of universalizing Russian as a national language. Moreover, there are issues related to lifestyle and social evils such as addiction (alcohol and drug), crime, educational level and sustainability of families, etc. The universality of Russian language among ethnic minorities has increasingly demonstrated the process of building common values of the Russian nation – people in general.

Regarding belief and religion, according to a survey conducted in 2013, 68% of Russians follow Orthodox, 7% follow Muslim, about 5% follow Buddhism and other religions [1]. Extreme religion, international terrorism, and drug trafficking during the globalization are emerging issues in ethnic minorities of Russia, especially in the Central Asian Region. Religious extremism appears in many propaganda publications, on social media, especially Islamic politicians and ideologies. Extreme religion approaches the trend of separatism, violence, and terrorism in the context that the present world becomes a national security risk and is used by these elements as a tool to gain power and influence other political forces on the international forum.

The main sponsor of terrorism and extreme religion is the drug trading apparatus. This apparatus does not care about stability, on the contrary, the more unstable it is, the more favorable the drug apparatus is. Therefore, drug cartels fund armed groups, spark conflict points, sponsor terrorism and international extremist religions in order to leave the government with insufficient resources to fight the drug trading.

Tools to fight and prevent non-traditional security risks of ethnic minorities in the past time, which are focused on by the Russian Federation, are: taking predictive and preventive measures; disabling the terrorist forces; applying measures in the field of domestic security to detect and destroy

weapons, equipment and infrastructure of terrorist organizations; struggling to prevent terrorist funding sources, such as blockade of accounts of terrorist organizations and individuals as well as countries that sponsor terrorism, prohibiting forms of material support and assistance for terrorist organizations and individuals.

(6) Organized crime and corruption. Mistakes in the early stages of the process of economic reform, the weakness of management and examination, supervision of judicial agencies, the degradation of social morality are the factors that promote the development of organized crime. Organized crime is closely related to the underground economy. Furthermore, organized crime is a market-based structure that allows it to quickly adapt to changes. The market mechanism opens up good opportunities for organized crime in the Russian Federation to develop. Organized crime in the Russian Federation is also expanding into the formal business sector thanks to the protection of government officials. Especially local authorities, autonomous regions and autonomous areas of many ethnic minorities.

Corruption and organized crime intertwine and rely on each other. Corruption destroys government structures, financial and business systems, which are dangerous obstacles to the democratic reform process. It reduces the effectiveness of national programs, threatens national interests, national security, and constitutional basis of citizens' rights and freedom. Corruption is both covering and encouraging organized crime. In recent years, ethnic minorities in the Russian Federation have become fertile ground for organized crime and corruption to hide, develop and rage.

Achievements in coping with negative impact of non-traditional security factors of ethnic minorities in the Russian Federation

The Russian Federation's existence and future as one of the largest countries in the territory, diverse and complex ethnic groups, rich and abundant natural resources in the world together with its own geostrategic location, always contains potential problems, challenges and risks. Particularly in the field

of national-ethnic construction, relations between ethnic groups, building a peaceful and harmonious relationship among ethnic groups in the Russian ethnic family, there are also problems and challenges that are non-traditional security, specifically:

Inequality in population distribution and national territory exploitation. Ethnic minorities are less developed, less populated but reside in larger and more remote areas. Loose relationship, production infrastructure and underdeveloped life generate a state of «far from» the center, socio-cultural isolation, including the evasive psychology, distance from the center, and consideration of the center as a different element in both the thinking and the lifestyle of the people. This is a serious challenge in building a united Russian culture, lifestyle and people in general.

Over the years, the movement of population in the Russian Federation towards the capital and its vicinity. The population migration is mainly Russian, the number of people who live in remote areas are mostly ethnic minorities. The movement of population to the capital and European region of the Russian Federation has made the population in remote areas, Syria and the Far East sparser.

The above-mentioned population trend causes polarization in the population distribution, potentially threatening both outside (from neighboring countries) and within (isolated nationalism, extremism, etc.). These trends threaten the existence of a united Russian Federation, a united Russian nation, including not only people in the central regions, Europe but also in Uran, Syria, Far East, etc. and promote the trend of social and cultural isolation between the Russians and ethnic minorities, but also hide the risk of extreme separatist and autonomous races.

This is a non-traditional security issue that is at risk of being transformed into traditional security and national security. Consequently, the Russian Federation pays special attention to dealing with these challenges. It is to increase investment in developing remote and isolated areas by national programs and projects in which attention is paid

on investing in infrastructure, encouraging production - business to life support and social incentives.

The results of socio-economic development programs in ethnic minority areas in recent years have been quite positive. Living conditions and living standards of the majority of ethnic minorities have been improved markedly and gradually approaching the national average living standard. In particular, some autonomous republic countries have recently contributed to the central budget.

Uniting the Russian peoples, building an image of an all-Russia united nation is a key strategy to solve the non-traditional security challenges that are of great concern. The Russian Federation is a multi-ethnic nation. Moreover, there are regions - autonomous regions in the form of autonomous republic countries, autonomous regions, etc. In the Russian Federation, there are always opposing tendencies. It is centripetal (national institutions such as the education system, the military, popular Russian language, the Russian mass media widely spread, etc.) to build a whole unified and centrifugal Russian Federation (institutions of the affiliated republic countries and localities keep the forms of organization of life and production in the traditional way of ethnic groups, religions, etc.) respect the independence of the republic countries and autonomous regions. Religions form differences in culture, worldview, and behavior of ethnic groups (ethnic characteristics or national characteristics). The efforts of the political world and the government is to build a national culture with its symbols and values to create the solidarity and unity of the Russian society. Inevitably, this is a long process of interaction, interaction and interaction among representatives of different nationalities, religions and beliefs within the framework of the united federal state. The decisive factor in ensuring the stability and consensus of ethnic groups is the state's policy and the operation of civil society's institutions.

In this respect, the state has an important role and responsibility. First of all, it is perfecting the legal system of the nation's ethnic policies, especially policies for ethnic

minorities. The rapid changes of Russian society in the fields of ethnicity, politics - society related to social stratification, mass migration, inequality and disparities among regions and regions in the market economy conditions create a basis for people's discontent, anxiety and insecurity in the future. That the Russian Federation becomes a host country for immigrants also creates many problems in harmonizing immigrants, adapting them, directing them to common values of the Russian Federation to ensure the national unity.

Strategic orientation in the coming time is to continue supporting and developing traditional forms of production and business, handicrafts, fine arts and other business activities according to the strengths of each locality and ethnic group (tourism to learn about ethnic culture, environmental protection, activities of preserving, restoring and protecting cultural and historical works).

The key strategy for the development of ethnic minority areas and ethnic minorities is the cadre policy, especially the management, business, communication, health, education and intellectual contingent. The training of a team of experts, scientists and art of ethnic minorities is currently being conducted at universities of republic countries, some training centers, including Moscow and Sant-Peterburg. Subjects of training and retraining are high school students, social activists and public employees of state agencies. To improve the quality of training, attention should be paid to the general education system, focusing on ethnic minority elements in general education (also teaching and training in ethnic minority languages).

Regarding constitutional and legal institutions, generally by 2030, the Russian Federation should keep stable the main contents of the present Constitution, including the federal state administrative institution. Among federal laws, it is necessary to enact the law on the national ethnic foundation and policy to ensure the national unity. This creates favorable conditions for the development of ethnic areas and ethnic minorities in the context of the current Russian Federation.

It is crucial to enact a federal law on the protection of ethnic minority and immigrant communities. This law should stipulate the rights of indigenous people in preserving the living environment and traditional economic forms as well as the responsibilities of business entities and the state when implementing programs and projects that may have a negative impact on the living and cultural conditions of indigenous communities (not just for ethnic minorities).

Lesson in dealing with the negative impacts of non-traditional ethnic minority security from the Russian Federation

Firstly, it is required to overcome the consequences of national policies from the Soviet period. On April 26, 1991, the Russian Federation enacted Law No. 1107-1 «On the restoration of the honor of the oppressed peoples». On April 21, 2014, the Russian President signed Ordinance No. 268 On the honor restoration measures of the peoples of Armenia, Bulgaria, Greece, Italy, Tatar Crimea and Germany and on state support to revive and develop (revised September 12, 2015), which set out the principle of ensuring equal conditions for the development and enrichment of all cultures of the peoples.

The program of rehabilitating oppressed ethnic minorities includes many activities, including investment in developing ethnic minority areas, solving existential issues such as land issues, building memorial areas for the victims, implementing program to restore the oppressed peoples, taking measures to ensure the right to vote, standing for election, and participating in central and local state power agencies; and supporting for spiritual and religious life. In the field of culture and language, ethnic minorities are interested in preserving and developing such as organizing teaching and learning in the general education system in ethnic languages, publishing cultural and artistic publications in ethnic languages; mass media in ethnic languages, etc.

Secondly, it is crucial to invest in the socio-economic development of ethnic minority areas. The Russian Government annually spends a large amount of money to

invest in socio-economic development of ethnic minority areas, republic countries and autonomous regions of ethnic minorities. The Russian Federation pays special attention to investing in infrastructure, especially transport infrastructure, railways, and motorways with the perspective that transport helps connect economic and promote economic – cultural – social exchanges, and narrowing the boundaries and gaps in development among peoples.

Every year, the Russian government also adopts many target programs with considerable budget to develop the sectors, fields and socio-economic aspects of ethnic minority areas with the goal of improving the lives, employment as well as social security for ethnic minority areas. In education and training, the Government has specific support mechanisms and policies such as recruitment, fee exemptions, subsidies, etc. or invests in renovating and upgrading education and training institutions. Also in the field of medicine and health care, besides investing in upgrading medical facilities, there are many other support policies in cash or in kind for medical examination and treatment of people.

Thirdly, it is essential to build a common value system across the Russian Federation as a foundation of national solidarity. In order to turn the multi-ethnic and multi-religious population structure into a source of development, the State of Russia is very interested in building values and common standards across the Russian Federation as a foundation for the national unity. This is the process of building unity in diversity.

The common value system of the Russian Federation as a basis for national solidarity is in the process of forming and building, but the government's interest in this process has been a favorable condition for the settlement of the relationship among peoples in the direction of harmony, stability and mutual assistance. In this direction, Russian language is an important tool. The promotion of learning and disseminating Russian language has the meaning of strengthening the links, the bonds and the mutual understanding of ethnic groups. By univer-

salizing the Russian language and promoting the process of disseminating and spreading Russian culture as a common and common value, is a point to unite the peoples living in the territory of the Russian Federation.

Fourthly, it is needed to handle non-traditional security issues with policy and law tools. Laws and policies are the main tools for the Russian government to manage non-traditional security issues in ethnic minority areas. In general, the Russian Federation is always interested in regulating independent religious activities by institutions, laws and policies. In 1997, the Russian Federation enacted a law on freedom of belief and religious organizations. In 2002, the country enacted the law against extremist activities. These are legal frameworks for managing religious activities and preventing abuse of ethnic and religious issues to incite violence, extremist religion, and terrorism. In 2016, the Russian government adopted a package of law amendments to intensify its fight against terrorism (often called the Iarova package). The revised package expands the scope of application and punishment for violations of the Law on Freedom of Belief and Religious Organizations. Accordingly, any religious activities that is not registered and not authorized by the government is illegal.

Besides issuing laws, mechanisms and policies, the Russian Federation is also particularly interested in the implementation with the involvement of authorities from the central to local levels. The Russian government attaches great importance to educational, deterrent and preventive measures. In

order to do that, besides extensive propaganda, the authorities at all levels also regularly conduct the inspection, examination and supervision, thereby, taking corrective measures, reminders and warnings. Concurrently, the functional forces promptly take strong measures with opposing acts, especially terrorist plots and tricks, from investigations, prosecutions, trials to preventive measures to hinder funding sources, destroying terrorist training and training facilities.

Fifthly, it is required to strengthen international cooperation in handling non-traditional security issues. The international cooperation in handling non-traditional security issues, such as cross-border smuggling, cross-border drug trafficking, women and child trafficking with foreign elements, climate change, deals on energy, resources and transnational crime. Especially, the international cooperation in terrorism prevention is highly valued by the Russian government, including cooperation on multilateral and bilateral forums. The cooperative areas are diverse and from exchanging experience in handling, information, especially intelligence to cooperation in counterterrorism campaigns.

The Russian Federation attaches special importance to cooperation with countries in the region, especially those in the post-Soviet space to fight against terrorism. The terrorism prevention in the Russian Federation is closely linked to the inhabited areas of ethnic minorities. Therefore, the tackling and terrorism issue cannot be separated from solving problems raised in ethnic minority areas in regional and international relations.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Этническое и религиозное многообразие России / под ред. В. А. Тишкова, В. В. Степанова. М.: ИЭА РАН, 2017. 551 с. URL: http://static.iea.ras.ru/news/Ethnicheskoe_i_religioznoe_mnogoobrazie_Rossii.pdf
2. Батюк В. И. Мировая политика: учебник для академического бакалавриата. Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2019. 256 с. URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/433675>
3. Этнический состав населения. Народы России // География. URL: <https://geographyofrussia.com/etnicheskij-sostav-naseleniya-narody-rossii/>

REFERENCES (TRANSLITERATED)

1. Jetnicheskoe i religioznoe mnogoobrazie Rossii / pod red. V. A. Tishkova, V. V. Stepanova. M.: IJeA RAN, 2017. 551 s. URL: http://static.iea.ras.ru/news/Ethnicheskoe_i_religioznoe_mnogoobrazie_Rossii.pdf
2. Batjuk V. I. Mirovaja politika: uchebnik dlja akademicheskogo bakalavriata. Moskva: Izdatel'stvo Jurajt, 2019. 256 s. URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/433675>
3. Jetnicheskij sostav naselenija. Narody Rossii // Geografija. URL: <https://geographyofrussia.com/etnicheskij-sostav-naseleniya-narody-rossii/>

Поступила в редакцию 25.05.2020.
Принята к публикации 28.05.2020.

Для цитирования:

Nguyen Linh Khieu Coping with negative impacts of non-traditional security in ethnic minority areas in Russian Federation and experience for Vietnam // Гуманитарный научный вестник. 2020. №5. С. 148-155. URL: <http://naukavestnik.ru/doc/2020/05/NguyenLinhKhieu.pdf>